

Novel flavone glycoside from *Ougeinia dalbergioides* (Benth.)

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Abstract : A novel flavone glycoside (m.p. 287–288 °C), C₃₆H₄₆O₂₁, [M]⁺ 814 (FABMS), was obtained from ethyl acetate soluble fraction of the ethanolic extract of the pods of *Ougeinia dalbergioides* (Benth.). It was characterized as 5,4'-dihydroxy-3,6,7,8-tetramethoxyflavone-5-O- α -L-rhamnopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 3)-O- α -L-arabinopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 4)-O- β -D-galactopyranoside by various chemical degradations and spectral analysis.

Keywords : *Ougeinia dalbergioides* (Benth.), Leguminosae, flavone, glycoside.

Ougeinia dalbergioides (Benth.) (N-O Leguminosae)^{1,2} is commonly known as Sandan or Tinsa in Hindi. It is found in the Central India, Orissa, Bombay and Marwar of Rajputana. Ayurvedic system of medicine describes that its bark is acrid, anthelmintic, astringents to the bowels, cures "Kapha and Vata". It is also used in the treatment of dysentery, leucoderma, urinary discharges, ulcers, blood diseases and skin diseases. Earlier workers³ have reported various components from heart wood of this plant.

Results and discussion

A novel compound **1**, m.p. 287–288 °C, C₃₆H₄₆O₂₁, [M]⁺ 814 (FABMS), was crystallised from ethanol as light brown crystalline needles. It gave positive response to Molisch and Shinoda⁴ tests indicating it to be flavonoidal glycoside. The UV spectrum of **1** showed two peaks at 258 and 360 nm relative to MeOH, which are characteristic of flavonoids⁵. A bathochromic shift of 22 nm in band 1, on addition of AlCl₃ relative to MeOH confirmed the presence of hydroxyl group at C-4' position⁶. A bathochromic shift of 20 nm in band 1 on addition of AlCl₃/HCl relative to methanol confirmed the presence of hydroxyl group at C-5 position⁷. Formation of 2,4-dihydroxy-1,5,6-trimethoxy benzene and *p*-hydroxy benzoic acid on alkaline degradation also confirmed the presence of one -OH group at C-5 position in ring A and another -OH group at C-4' position in ring B. In ¹³C NMR spectrum, a chemical shift at δ 182.03 of the carbonyl carbon atom at C-4 position also confirmed the presence of hydroxyl group at C-5 position.

Acid hydrolysis of compound **1** yielded an aglycone **2**, m.p. 224–226 °C, C₁₉H₁₈O₈, [M]⁺ *m/z* 274 (FABMS), identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-3,6,7,8-tetramethoxy flavone by comparison of its m.p., UV, IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and MS data with reported literature values⁸. The hydrolysate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination showed the presence of D-galactose (*R_f* 0.17), L-arabinose (*R_f* 0.22) and L-rhamnose (*R_f* 0.36) by (Co-PC)⁹.

In ¹H NMR spectrum, a doublet appeared at δ 8.08, was assigned for H-2' and H-6'. Four singlets found at δ 3.90, 3.92, 3.95 and 3.98 confirmed the presence of -OCH₃ groups at C-3, C-6, C-7 and C-8 positions respectively¹⁰. A multiplet at δ 2.09–2.48 of 24 proton intensity was found for sugar acetoxyl. Characteristic signals of anomeric protons of sugars were observed at δ 5.47 (1H, d, *J* 2.00 Hz, H-1''), 5.07 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, H-1'''), 5.33 (1H, d, *J* 2.00 Hz, H-1''') and 1.06 (3H, d, *J* 6.00 Hz, rhamnosyl methyl). The location of sugars at C-5 was supported by ¹³C NMR of **1** (see Experimental). In ¹³C NMR spectrum four signals at δ 59.10, 60.12, 60.96 and 61.32 each of 3 proton intensity were assigned to methoxy groups at C-3, C-6, C-7, C-8 positions respectively. In mass spectra, a base peak at *m/z* 358 [M⁺-CH₃], is characteristic of 3-methoxy flavone. The RDA fragment at *m/z* 121 and 182 showed the presence of one hydroxyl group at C-4' position in ring B and another hydroxyl group at C-5 position in ring A of the aglycone **2**. In ¹³C NMR, chemical shift at δ 163.48 for C-2, 139.80 for C-3 and 182.03 for C-4 were indicative for 3-O-methyl etherification¹¹.

Permethylation¹² of compound **1** with (MeI/Ag₂O/DMF) followed by acid hydrolysis with 10% HCl afforded methylated aglycone **4**, m.p. 249–250 °C, C₂₀H₂₀O₈, [M]⁺ *m/z* 388 (FABMS), identified as 5-hydroxy-3,6,7,8,4'-pentamethoxy flavone by its ¹H NMR, UV and IR spectral data (see Experimental) which confirmed that glycosidation was involved at C-5 position of the aglycone. The methylated sugars were identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose (*R*_G 1.00), 2,4-di-*O*-methyl-L-arabinose (*R*_G 0.65) and 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose (*R*_G 0.70)⁹ (Co-PC). It concludes that C-1'''' of L-rhamnose was attached with C-3''' of L-arabinose, C-1''' of L-arabinose was linked with C-4'' of D-galactose and C-1'' of D-galactose was attached with C-5 OH of the aglycone. Thus inter sugar glycosidic linkages (1→3) and (1→4) were found between L-rhamnose and L-arabinose as well as between L-arabinose and D-galactose respectively¹³.

Quantitative estimation of sugar according to the procedure of Mishra and Rao¹⁴ revealed that all the three sugars were present in equimolar ratio (1 : 1 : 1). Periodate oxidation¹⁵ of **1** confirmed that all the sugars were present in the pyranose form.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of **1** with enzyme takadiastase yielded L-rhamnose, first, followed by L-arabinose and proaglycone **5**, identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-3,6,7,8-tetramethoxy-5-*O*-β-D-galactopyranoside, m.p. 206–208 °C, C₂₅H₂₈O₁₃ [M]⁺ 536 (see in Experimental), confirming the presence of α-linkage between L-rhamnose and L-arabinose as well as between L-arabinose and D-galactose. Enzymatic hydrolysis of proaglycone with almond emulsin gave aglycone and D-galactose revealing the presence of β-linkage between D-galactose and aglycone.

On the basis of above evidences, compound **1** was identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-3,6,7,8-tetramethoxy flavone 5-*O*-α-*l*-rhamnopyranosyl(1→3)-*O*-α-*l*-arabinopyranosyl(1→4)-*O*-β-D-galactopyranoside.

Experimental

General experimental procedure : All the melting points were determined by soft capillary tube in thermoelectric m.p. apparatus and are uncorrected. The IR spectra were recorded on Shimadzu 8201 PC spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker DRX 300 NMR spectrometer and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at 90 MHz using (DMSO-*d*₆) as solvent. UV spectra were recorded on UV/VIS Hitachi 320 Perkin Elmer Lambda 15 spectrophotometer and mass spectra on a Jeol SX-102 (FAB) mass spectrometer.

Plant material : The pods of *O. dalbergioides* (Benth.) were collected from the Satpura Hills (Betul) in M.P. (India) and was identified by Taxonomist, Department of Botany, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar (M.P.), India. A voucher specimen has been deposited in the Chemistry Department of this University.

Extraction and Isolation : Dried, powdered pods (3 kg) of *O. dalbergioides* (Benth.) were extracted with 95% ethanol in the Soxhlet extractor and the alcoholic extract was concentrated under reduced pressure to yield dark brown viscous mass which was successively partitioned with petroleum ether (60–80 °C), CHCl₃, EtOAc, Ac₂O and MeOH. The EtOAc soluble part was concentrated and subjected to TLC using solvents (CHCl₃ : MeOH : H₂O, 8 : 4 : 2) and iodine vapours as visualizing agent. It gave two spots indicating it to be mixture of two compounds **1** and **3**. These were separated by TLC and purified by column chromatography, preparative TLC and studied separately. Compound **3** was found in very small quantity therefore it was rejected.

Study of compound **1** :

Compound **1** crystallized from ethanol as light brown crystalline needles (1.850 g) m.p. 287–288 °C, C₃₆H₄₆O₂₁, [M]⁺ 814, (FABMS) (Found : C, 53.72; H, 5.67. Calcd. for C₃₆H₄₆O₂₁ : C, 53.68; H, 5.62%); IR ν_{max} (KBr) 3346 (OH), 2924 (C–H stretching), 2863 (OMe), 1652 (α,β-unsaturated C=O), 1625 (aromatic ring system), 1245 (C–O–C stretching), 1062 (*O*-glycosidic linkage), 867 (two adjacent H-atoms), 825 (two adjacent C atoms in benzene ring); UV (MeOH) λ_{max} 233, 278, 340 (+AlCl₃), 245, 288, 362 (AlCl₃/HCl), 258, 288, 310, 360; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) of **1** at δ 3.90 (3H, s, 3-OMe), 3.92 (3H, s, 6-OMe), 3.95 (3H, s, 7-OMe), 3.98 (3H, s, 8-OMe), 7.58 (1H, d, *J* 10.0 Hz, H-4), 7.42 (1H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz, H-5), 8.08 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.01 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 2.42 (1H, s, 4'-OH), 5.47 (1H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz, H-1''-galactose), 3.76–4.15 (5H, m, H-2'', H-3'', H-4'', H-5'', H-6''), 5.07 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz, H-1'''' anomeric proton of L-arabinose), 4.40–5.05 (4H, m, H-2''', H-3''', H-4''', H-5'''), 5.33 (1H, d, *J* 2.00 Hz, H-1'''' anomeric proton of L-rhamnose), 3.58–3.65 (4H, m, H-2''', H-3''', H-4''', H-5'''), 1.06 (3H, d, *J* 6.00 Hz, rhamnosyl methyl), 5.50–6.53 (10H, m, sugar protons); ¹³C NMR (90 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) δ 163.45 (C-2), 139.8 (C-3), 182.03 (C-4), 151.90 (C-5), 135.32 (C-6), 144.05 (C-7), 132.12 (C-8), 147.53 (C-9), 105.68 (C-10), 120.85 (C-1'), 109.52 (C-2'), 120.95 (C-3'), 155.5 (C-4'), 115.41 (C-5'), 119.86 (C-6'), 59.1 (3-OMe), 60.12 (6-OMe), 60.96 (7-OMe), 61.32 (8-OMe), 105.20 (C-1''), 72.10 (C-2''),

1

2

4

5

75.43 (C-3''), 68.94 (C-4''), 60.84 (C-5''), 66.5 (C-6''), 100.36 (C-1'''), 69.72 (C-2'''), 77.10 (C-3'''), 60.48 (C-4'''), 59.68 (C-5'''), 101.50 (C-1''''), 72.20 (C-2''''), 72.11 (C-3''''), 73.42 (C-4''''), 69.51 (C-5''''), 67.32 (C-6''''); MS (FABMS) $[M]^+$ 814 absent $[M^+ - L\text{-rhamnose } m/z 146]^+$, 668 $[L\text{-arabinose } m/z 132]^+$, 536 $[D\text{-galactose } m/z 162]^+$, 374 absent $[M-H]^+$ 373, $[-CH_2]^+$ 359, $[-H]^+$ 358, $[-CO]^+$ 330, $[-H]^+$ 329, $[-CH_2]^+$ 315, $[-H]^+$ 314, $[-CH_2]^+$ 300, $[-H]^+$ 299, $[-CH_2]^+$ 285, 227, 226, 211, 182, 121, 118, 94.

Acid hydrolysis of compound 1 :

Compound 1 (400 mg) was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and refluxed with 20 ml of 10% H_2SO_4 on water bath for 6–7 h. The contents were concentrated and allowed to cool and residue was extracted with diethyl ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and chromatographed over silica gel column using $CHCl_3 : MeOH$ (4 : 6) to yield compound 2 (250 mg), m.p. 224–226 °C, $C_{19}H_{18}O_8$, $[M]^+$ m/z 374 (Found : C, 60.94; H, 4.81. Calcd. for $C_{19}H_{18}O_8$: C, 60.96; H 4.80%) which was identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-3,6,7,8-tetramethoxy flavone by comparison of its known spectral data with reported

literature values. The aqueous hydrolysate was neutralized with $BaCO_3$ and $BaSO_4$ filtered off. The filtrate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination using n-BAW (4 : 1 : 5) as solvent and aniline hydrogen phthalate as detecting agent, confirmed the presence of D-galactose (R_f 0.17), L-arabinose (R_f 0.22) and L-rhamnose (R_f 0.36).

Permethylation of compound 1 :

The compound 1 (40 mg) was treated with MeI (5 ml) and Ag_2O (5 mg) in dimethyl formamide (10 ml) in a 150 ml conical flask and left for 48 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was filtered, washed with DMF and then hydrolysed with 10% ethanolic H_2SO_4 to give methylated aglycone 4, m.p. 249–250 °C, $C_{20}H_{20}O_8$, $[M]^+$ m/z 388 (Found : C, 67.14; H, 5.81. Calcd. for $C_{20}H_{20}O_8$: C, 67.04; H 5.87%); IR ν_{max} (KBr) 3348, 2922, 2865, 1650, 1624, 1242, 1062, 865, 824; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 3.88 (3H, s, 3-OMe), 3.90 (3H, s, 6-OMe), 3.93 (3H, s, 7-OMe), 3.97 (3H, s, 8-OMe), 3.84 (3H, s, 4'-OMe), 7.58 (1H, d, J 10.0 Hz, H-4), 7.43 (1H, d, J 10.2 Hz, H-5), 8.08 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.01 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3', H-5'). Thus the methylated aglycone was identified as 5-hydroxy-3,6,7,8,4'-pentamethoxy flavone and methylated sugars were identified as 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-L-rhamnose, 2,4-di-*O*-methyl-L-arabinose and 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose.

Study of proaglycone 5 :

It had m.p. 206–207 °C, $C_{25}H_{28}O_{13}$, $[M]^+$ 536 (FABMS) (Found : C, 55.93; H, 5.25. Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{28}O_{13}$: C, 55.97; H, 5.22%); IR ν_{max} (KBr) 3346, 2924, 2866, 1652, 1625, 1244, 1064, 866, 825; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) δ 3.87 (3H, s, 3-OMe), 3.89 (3H, s, 6-OMe), 3.91 (3H, s, 7-OMe), 3.96 (3H, s, 8-OMe), 3.83 (3H, s, 4'-OMe), 7.60 (1H, d, J 10.1 Hz, H-4), 7.41 (1H, d, J 10.2 Hz, H-5), 8.06 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-2', H-6'), 7.00 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3', H-5'), 5.47 (1H, d, J 7.8 Hz, H-1'' anomeric proton of galactose), 3.76–4.15 (5H, m, H-2'', H-3'', H-4'', H-5'', H-6''). Thus it was identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-3,6,7,8-tetramethoxy flavone 5-*O*- β -D-galactopyranoside.

Alkaline degradation of aglycone 2 :

Compound 2 (30 mg) was treated with 50% KOH (10 ml) in EtOH (5 ml) for 36 h. The contents were cooled and neutralized with 7% HCl and extracted with Et_2O . The ethereal layer was treated with 50% $NaHCO_3$ solution and the aqueous portion on acidification yielded a

compound **2b** *para* hydroxy benzoic acid, m.p 213–214 °C, C₇H₆O₃, [M]⁺ 138 (Found : C, 68.65; H, 4.38. Calcd. for C₇H₆O₃ : C, 68.68; H, 4.36%), identified as *para* hydroxy benzoic acid. The aqueous phase was treated with 10% NaOH and on acidification gave compound **2a**, m.p. 140–141 °C, C₉H₁₂O₅, [M]⁺ 200 (Found : C, 54.02; H, 6.05. Calcd. for C₉H₁₂O₅ : C, 54.00; H, 6.00%), identified as 2,4-dihydroxy-1,5,6-trimethoxy benzene.

Enzymatic hydrolysis of compound **1** :

15 mg of the compound **1** was dissolved in MeOH (25 ml) and hydrolysed with equal volume of takadiastase at room temperature in 100 ml round bottomed flask fitted with air condenser. The reaction mixture was left for 3 days at room temperature and filtered and studied separately.

The hydrolysate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination using n-BAW (4 : 1 : 5) as solvent and aniline hydrogen phthalate a detecting agent confirmed the presence of L-rhamnose (*R_f* 0.36), L-arabinose (*R_f* 0.22) (Co-PC).

The proglycone (5 mg) was dissolved in MeOH (20 ml) and hydrolysed with equal volume of almond emulsin as above procedure and filtered. The aglycone was identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-3,6,7,8-tetramethoxy flavone. The hydrolysate was concentrated and subjected to paper chromatography examination a usual procedure showed the presence of D-galactose (*R_f* 0.17).

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